

Exploring Different Approaches to the Suburb Concept: A Case Study of Vilnius City

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Abstract.

The article addresses the issue of territorial classification of urban areas using Vilnius, the capital of Lithuania, as an example. In Lithuania, settlements are categorized into two types: urban areas (designated as cities) and rural areas (which include towns, villages, and homesteads). Vilnius is the largest city in Lithuania, with a population of nearly 600,000 residents, while the smallest town, Panemune, has ca. 200 inhabitants. It is evident that the current classification system is flawed and does not optimally represent the territory. The fact that the population difference between the largest and smallest urban settlements exceeds a factor of 3,000, while their administrative status remains identical, highlights a significant inconsistency in the current territorial classification system. Additionally, the definition of suburban areas is not clearly established in Lithuania, leading to varied interpretations and resulting in significantly different outcomes in classification. The aim of this article is to examine several examples of suburbanization and illustrate how these varying definitions can distort population statistics. To achieve data-driven solutions and sustainable development, it is essential to rely on statistics that are aggregated into appropriate territorial units.

Submission Type. Case study.

BoK Concepts. [GS3] Use of geospatial information; [AM4] Basic analytical operations; [GD2] Data Collection.

Keywords. city, suburb, urban periphery, GIS, urban development.

1 Introduction

The concept of suburbs is used across various disciplines – spatial planning, geography, and urban studies – yet it is interpreted differently depending on the field. Terms such as suburb, urban influence area, area of integrity, metropolitan region, and functional urban area are often used interchangeably, though they differ in meaning and criteria. Definitions and boundaries are rarely clear, and there is a lack of consistency in the application of geographical data and spatial analysis methods.

The Lithuanian Encyclopaedia defines a suburb as the areas on the outskirts of a city. A scientific monograph published in 2017 and devoted to Lithuania's metropolitan regions (Burneika et. al, 2017) mentions that there exist cities and suburbs, although the latter are not exclusively urban'. The main factors used to distinguish suburbs are: the number of inhabitants, their positive change, the number of individual houses and the year of their construction. The explanatory material of the General Plan of the Vilnius City Municipality does not explicitly define suburbs, but provides a map showing these areas (Vilnius City Municipality, 2020). Annex 5 of the description of the procedure for monitoring the preparation and implementation of sustainable urban development strategies and functional area strategies specifies areas that meet the criterion of distinguishable integrity, which are broadly understood as suburbs (Ministry of the Interior of the Republic of Lithuania, 2024). The concept of distinguishable integrity refers to the classification of territories according to the distribution of built-up areas and demographic indicators.

At the European level, functional urban areas include cities and their commuting zones (Dijkstra et al., 2019), while Eurostat identifies metropolitan regions based on population density (Eurostat, 2018). Thus, there are many different methodologies to distinguish suburban areas. The example of Vilnius is chosen because it is the largest city in Lithuania, its capital and an important city in the European context.

Accurately identifying suburban areas remains a complex task with implications for urban planning and statistical analysis. As Pacione (2009) argued, understanding urban geography requires looking beyond city boundaries. This perspective is increasingly relevant as urban functions expand into rural areas, a trend observed more than a decade ago (Ubarevičienė et al., 2010–2011; Cirtautas, 2013). However, this transformation is still often described qualitatively rather than defined through consistent, data-driven criteria. The aim of this article is not to delineate suburbs, but to

highlight the methodological differences and show how varying approaches affect population statistics.

2 Data and Methods

The main objective of the study is to directly evaluate the disparities resulting from the different territorial differentiation in Lithuania. It has never been done before.

2.1 Data preparation

The preparation of spatial data for this research was conducted in two phases:

1. Spatial data preparation for suburban areas. Some of the data for the different classifications described in the introductory chapter are publicly and openly available. The other part is available as screenshots and figures in scientific articles or documents.
2. Preparation of population and housing census data to see differences between the different classifications.

2.2 Data and Software Availability

This study uses data from the Address Register of the Republic of Lithuania as of October 2024 and the 2021 Census of Population and Housing of the Republic of Lithuania. Both data sources are available as open data and can be freely accessed by the public. Although commercial software was used for data processing, all applied methods are fully replicable using virtually any GIS software.

2.3 Methods

The logical and comparative methods of analysis are crucial for this study. As previously noted, both the treatment of suburbs and the definitions used to describe them vary significantly. To identify at least some comparable territorial units, it is essential to evaluate these different definitions and determine whether suburban areas are considered part of a metropolitan region, a functional region, or other categories.

Methods of data selection, aggregation and compression were used as implemented in GIS software packages. Basic cartographic techniques were used to visualise suburban areas.

The aggregation method was used for the calculation of population statistics. Unfortunately, detailed statistical information on the areas identified by the different classifications is either not available or not up-to-date. For this reason, the most up-to-date data from the Population

and Housing Census have been aggregated to the same areas for all classifications. To compare the statistical indicators, absolute and percentage changes were calculated between the different classifications.

3 Results

Two main results of the study are:

- a) the suburban areas identified by the different methods represented on maps, and
- b) the population statistics aggregated in these areas and their differences highlighted.

3.1 Suburbs

The vector data of suburbs was created (Figure 1). The official boundary municipality of Vilnius City is indicated by red contour and label “1”. Its territory is included in the areas calculated by various methods. Other labels indicate the ‘suburban’ territories estimated using different sets of criteria:

“2” – the territory meeting the criteria of integrity (Ministry of the Interior of the Republic of Lithuania, 2024b);

“3” – the territory treated as a suburban area in the monograph of Lithuanian geographers (Burneika et. al., 2017b);

“4” – the territory identified in the explanatory material of the General Plan of the Vilnius City Municipality (Vilnius City Municipality, 2020b);

“5” – the functional areas of the city (Dijkstra et. al., 2019b)

“6” represents the Vilnius metropolitan region as identified by Eurostat (Eurostat, 2018b).

Figure 1. Suburbs of Vilnius City according to different methodologies and classifications.

All maps are at a scale of 1:1 000 000. However, it is quite difficult to visually assess the magnitude of the changes using different methodologies and classifications. The first table shows the size of the identification areas and the share of Vilnius municipality in them.

Table 1. Size of the estimated suburban areas and the ratio of Vilnius municipality–suburbs.

Territory number	Area	
	Suburban area, km ²	Size, compared to Vilnius City, %
1	0	–
2	140	35
3	1553	388
4	2796	699
5	3846	962
6	9329	2332

The differences presented in the table only serve to illustrate the different criteria used to distinguish suburbs. It is important to note that the differences are significant even when comparing the methods used in Lithuania to distinguish suburban areas.

3.2 Population statistics

The total population of the suburbs identified by the different methods was calculated (Figure 2). The variation in population is not as uniform as in the case of the areas. Area 2 is about 35% larger than Area 1, while the population is only about 8% larger. In the case of the sixth area, the area increases by a factor of almost 25 and the population by a factor of only about 0.5. These

statistics are particularly important for a better understanding of areas that should be considered to be suburbs. While the area 1, area 2 and area 3 aims to include relatively densely populated areas, the areas from 4 to 6 encompass large regions that are mostly uninhabited.

Figure 2. Population in the suburbs identified by different methods

The distribution of the population by education also varies across the suburbs delineated by different methods. While in the areas from 1 to 3 the difference in the number of people with higher education is only about 2–3%, in the areas from 4 to 6 the differences can be as high as 7%. The suburbs are not completely identical to the city, but the population structure should, at least in theory, be quite similar.

Figure 3. Population with higher education percentage in the suburbs identified by different methods

The breakdown by occupational group also provides a better understanding of changes in the structure of the population. In addition, urban dwellers are less likely to be employed in agriculture, forestry and fishing. The second table shows the number of professionals in these sectors. It can be seen that the first methods do not change the structure very much, but the differences are very large for the other methods. The sixth field is generally out of context.

Table 2. Skilled workers in agriculture, forestry and the fishing industry

Territory number	Territory size, km ²	% of total population employed in listed areas
1	400	0,28
2	540	0,30
3	1953	0,41
4	3196	0,50
5	4246	0,59
6	9729	1,08

4 Conclusion and Future Research

The study revealed that various methodologies exist for identifying suburban areas. These methodologies are being developed both within individual countries and at the European level. However, when comparing all the methodologies in the same context, significant differences emerge, and there is no universally accepted approach for defining suburbs.

The majority of methodologies are based solely on population size aggregated into relatively large territorial units. In these days of detailed spatial data (big data), this does not seem to be efficient. It is essential to evaluate the spatial data and analysis methods that could enhance the identification and delineation of suburban areas.

A study is planned to develop a clear, coherent and practical methodology for the differentiation of the Lithuanian territory based on detailed spatial data and modern spatial analysis and cartographic methods. It is hoped that such a methodology could be modified and applied on a European or even global scale.

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